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WAVELET ANALYSIS METHOD FOR DEFECTS DETECTION IN CFRP WITH FULLY NON-CONTACT LAMB WAVES SYSTEM

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Introduction

- The importance of **Ultrasonic Testing** for CFRP industry and research

Global Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) Market Share, By Technique, 2021

[1]

[2]

- Time-consumption: the biggest **disadvantage** of conventional Ultrasonic Testing systems

- Lamb Waves propagation** as a promising technique for the improvement of Ultrasonic Testing systems
- In this study, the development of **signal algorithms adapted to a novel Lamb Waves control system** is investigated

[1] Fortune Business insights « Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) market »

[2] <http://www.worldofndt.com> « Introduction to ultrasonic testing »

[3] <https://www.gnes.co.jp/en/>

Lamb Waves testing

- **Lamb Waves:** mechanical waves propagating in the in-plane directions of thin structures
- Two infinite sets of **propagation modes** which velocity is highly dependent on the wave frequency

- Lamb Waves **defects detection system:**

1. Excitation of the Lamb Waves
 2. Propagation and interaction with the medium
 3. Reception (measurement) of the waves
 4. Signal Processing of the measured signal to obtain information
- Challenges and **research leads**
 - In **this study:**
 - **Laser-Induced Plasma Shock Wave**
 - Plates with several types of **artificial delamination**
 - **Signal Processing algorithm** based on a **Wavelet Transform analysis**

Experimental samples

- **Two types of samples:** stiffened with large delamination and flat with small round delamination
- **Quasi-isotropic** lay-up
- **Artificial defects** created by insertion of Teflon film

CFRP properties

E1 [GPa]	E2 [GPa]	v12	v23
152	8.0	0.34	0.54
G12 [GPa]	G23 [GPa]	Density [kg/m ³]	Ply thickness [mm]
4.03	2.52	1539	0.2

- **Stiffened samples lay-up: [45/0/-45/90]s (bottom) + [-45/0/45/90]s (top)**

LW-08-08-00

LW-08-08-75S

LW-08-08-50S

- **Small delamination sample lay-up: [45/0/-45/90]2s**

LW-16-00-siz

LW-32-00-dep

Defects detail:

Experimental set-up

Laser properties:
 Nd:YAG pulse laser
 λ 1064 nm
 Beam dia 9.5 mm
 Pulse width 5 ns
 Max output 850 mJ

1. Focalisation of laser by lens
2. Generation of a plasma at a distance d from the sample's surface + generation of shock waves
3. Shock waves encountering the surface generate a propagation of Lamb Waves
4. A Single Laser Doppler Vibrometer (SLDV) measures the out-of-plane surface displacement

Data acquisition

- At each measurement point, the SLDV records the **particle out-of-plane displacement over time**

- Measurement of different zones:
 - Baseline** zones
 - Control-line** zones

LW-08-08-00

LW-08-08-50S

LW-08-08-75S

LW-16-00-siz

LW-32-00-dep

Signal Processing algorithm

Algorithm details in appendix

Calculation of Damage Indexes

MAD: Mean Absolute Difference

Mean cwt value in the time-frequency domain of the absolute difference matrix at each surface point

Wave velocity

Velocity calculated from the time-of-arrival of the Lamb Wave signal at each surface point

RMSE: Root Mean Squared Error

Root Mean Squared Error of each pixel of the time-frequency images of baseline and control-line

$$RMSE(X) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (i_{baseline} - i_{control\ line})^2}$$

SDI: Structural Dissimilarity Index

Structural Dissimilarity Index of each pixel of the time-frequency images of baseline and control-line

$$SDI = \frac{1}{2} (1 - l(BL, CL) \times c(BL, CL) \times s(BL, CL))$$

$$l(BL, CL) = \frac{(2\mu_{BL}\mu_{CL} + c_1)}{(\mu_{BL}^2 + \mu_{CL}^2 + c_1)}$$

$$s(BL, CL) = \frac{(COV_{BLCL} + c_3)}{(\sigma_{BL}\sigma_{CL} + c_3)}$$

$$c(BL, CL) = \frac{(2\sigma_{BL}\sigma_{CL} + c_2)}{(\sigma_{BL}^2 + \sigma_{CL}^2 + c_2)}$$

Results: stiffened samples

LW-08-08-50S

LW-08-08-75S

Results: small delamination samples

LW-16-00-siz

LW-32-00-dep

Results: quantitative analysis (1/2)

LW-08-08-50S

LW-08-08-75S

Results: quantitative analysis (2/2)

LW-16-00-siz

LW-16-00-siz

LW-32-00-dep

LW-32-00-dep

Conclusion

- Innovative system using **Laser-Induced Plasma Shock Wave** for the generation of Lamb Waves in CFRP composites
- Development of efficient **Signal Processing method** to adapt this wave excitation system
 - Wavelet Analysis of the signals
 - Extraction of Damage Indexes based on time-frequency data and on image processing
 - Optimization and visualization of the Probability Function
- Validation of the ability to **qualitatively detect artificial defects**
- Quantitatively, still not as efficient as conventional UT method
- Leads for the **next improvements**:
 - Generating better baselines with numerical simulation
 - Investigating new DIs
 - Extending the database and eventually exploiting deep learning

Appendix 1: Data acquisition details

Sample type	Recording time t_{\max} [μs]	Sampling frequency F_s [MHz]	Time samples T_s	Passband filter [kHz]
Stiffened samples	800	2.56	2048	[8 – 600]
Small delamination sample	1600	3.125	5000	[10 – 600]

Appendix 2: Wavelet Analysis

STEP 1:
EXTENSION OF THE DATA
IN MULTI-DOMAIN USING
WAVELET ANALYSIS

Appendix 3: Calculation of Damage Indexes

STEP 2:
CALCULATION OF
DAMAGE
INDEXES (DIS)

Analysis of **spatial-frequency image**: DI calculation for each t_i value
 ▶ Curve of DI evolution with time

Analysis of **spatial-time image**: DI calculation for each f_i value
 ▶ Curve of DI evolution with frequency

Analysis of **frequency-time image**: DI calculation for each d value
 ▶ Cartography of DI at each sample point of distance d_i

Appendix 4: Optimization of the Probability Function

- Definition of a first Probability Function equation:

$$PF = \frac{1}{4} \left(\alpha \frac{RMSE}{RMSE_{max}} + \beta \frac{SDI}{SDI_{max}} + \gamma \frac{MAD}{MAD_{max}} + \varepsilon \frac{velocity}{velocity_{max}} \right)$$

- Genetic algorithm
 - Minimize PF - Ref
 - $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \varepsilon \in [0,1]$
 - $\alpha + \beta + \gamma + \varepsilon = 1$
- Reference:
 - PF = 1 in delamination zone
 - PF = 0 in healthy zone
- Result of the optimization algorithm:
 - $\alpha, \gamma, \varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ and $\beta \rightarrow 1$
 - SDI is the best Damage Index to generate reliable cartographies